

INSULATING LAYERED COMPOSITE MATERIALS MANUFACTURING AND THERMAL DIFFUSIVITY MEASUREMENTS

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1 Introduction [1, 2]

In the modern solid fuel rocket engines two or three layers of different materials are applied between fuel and combustion chamber body. The most significant is thermal insulation. Without this layer, solid fuel rocket engines would not have so wide range of operating. The other two layers are an inhibitor and a liner. The inhibitor protects the surface, on which it is applied, from combustion, what enables to control a pressure inside the combustion chamber, through changing combustion surface area. The liner connects fuel with thermal insulation. Most often liners have great thermal deformation capability.

Due to features, such as compact and simple construction, relatively easy storage conditions and instantaneous ready-to-use ability, in different terrain and atmospheric conditions, solid fuel rocket engines are used as a propulsion for machine gun bullets, control engines of middle- and long-range rockets. They are also used in take-off and primary propulsion systems of ballistic missiles, meteorological and geophysical rockets and in spacecrafts.

Propulsion charge and ignition systems are both placed in the combustion chamber. It has shape of light-wall, cylindrical tube and is designed for keeping possibly optimal fuel ignition and combustion conditions. Combustion chamber body is usually used as a base of rocket's supporting structure.

Basic load on the combustion chamber is usually a pressure force of gaseous combustion products, which vertically and horizontally affects internal surface of the combustion chamber. The engine is exposed to the strongest impact of forces during its initial operating moment

Intensive heating up of combustion chamber walls by hot combustion products, causes appearance of addition thermal stress and deteriorates endurance of

wall material [3, 4]. After short time, it can lead to an engine explosion, even if the pressure in the combustion chamber is lower than maximum, allowed, working pressure.

A layer of thermal insulation is applied on the internal side of the supporting wall, to prevent extraordinary increase of the average temperature of combustion chamber walls [5]. Thermal insulation layer should have possibly low density of the cover material and good adherence, while its endurance is not so important. Epoxy and phenolic resins work well in these applications.

One of the most important elements of the solid fuel rocket engines development are constantly improving mass characteristics. This development can be obtained thanks to implementation of new combustion chamber and nozzle construction materials. Metal is replaced, in constructions, by varied kinds of reinforced composites, which are durable and resistant to high temperature.

1.1 Requirements for thermal insulations [6]

Thermal insulation has to cope with strict requirements, such as:

- Low specific weight
- Chemical compatibility with fuel (no chemical reactivity)
- Low susceptibility to erosion
- Low thermal conductivity
- Good adherence to fuel surface covered with inhibitor
- Simple manufacturing of the whole insulation
- Low material degradation under influence of very high temperature
- Lack of oxidizing components
- Low thermal expansion
- Should be rigid and not combustible.

2. Motivation

RS-SSA has already used ready-made paper or polymer pipes and self-made composite pipes based on various kinds of papers and aqueous adhesives or resin sizes. All these solutions were good, but they were not strong enough to be used together with High Performance (HP) types of fuels in reusable rocket engines. It was decided to perform precise analysis for new materials that can be used in such an application. It was believed that it enables to use thinner layer of insulation, which should decrease its weight and raise the weight of fuel in such engine. It was decided to choose composite materials, from which it is easy to form insulating sleeve in the shape of a thin-wall pipe.

The composite material under investigation, which will become the insulating layer in take-off, solid fuel rocket engines, have to fulfill some assumptions:

- Hot gases will affect it for less than 4 seconds.
- Temperature in the combustion chamber, during engine operation, will be less than 3500°C.
- Thermal insulation will not transfer loads from pressure forces.
- Maximum work temperature of engine body is 100°C.
- Thermal insulation is disposable and will be replaced after each engine ignition.
- New HP fuel will contain Ammonium Perchlorate and Hydroxyl-terminated polybutadiene.

3. Samples composition materials and their properties

Insulating composites consists of resin matrix and various reinforcement. Four kinds of resin and five types of reinforcement were used to prepare samples. All prepared and measured materials and their names are presented in Table 1.

Matrixes under investigation, Table 3 presents physical properties of matrixes:

- Phenol-formaldehyde resin: MODOFEN TP (produced by ZCH Organika-Sarzyna)
- Phenol-formaldehyde resin: MODOFEN L (produced by ZCH Organika-Sarzyna)
- Epoxy resin: EPOLAM 2025 + hardener (produced by Amod)

- Phenol-formaldehyde resin: MODOFEN TP mixed with MODOFEN L (both produced by ZCH Organika-Sarzyna)

Reinforcements under investigation, Table 2 presents physical properties of reinforcements:

- Ceramic paper – Kaowool 1260 – 1mm thick (produced by Thermal Ceramics)
- Glass fiber
- Basalt fiber
- Wrapping paper

4. Samples manufacturing process

Composite materials, which were investigated, were prepared by Warsaw University of Technology students – members of the RS-SSA. Samples which contained heat-hardening resin, were thermally processed in the Composite Laboratory of the Faculty of Power and Aeronautical Engineering, Warsaw University of Technology.

All samples were prepared on the smooth surface of duralumin plates. Before a coat of liquid divider and the first layer of matrix were laid, surface of each plate had been cleaned and degreased with acetone. This ensured that no external particles got into first layer of matrix or disturbed divider functioning. A schema of work on each sample was almost the same. The main difference was a number of matrixes and reinforcement layers.

Little amount of each matrix – resin was put into separated plastic cups. That made application of them, using brush, much easier in the later processes. Recommended by producer amount of liquid hardener was added to epoxy resin EPOLAM 2025 and precisely mixed. Cups used for holding phenol-formaldehyde resins were made of polystyrene, these holding epoxy resin EPOLAM 2025 were made of polypropylene, because hardener dissolves polystyrene.

Bristle of brushes was additionally cut and checked to avoid single hair from getting into matrix. To prevent matrixes mixing, each type of matrix was applied using different brush. If the matrixes had got mixed, it would have undeniable influence on experiment results. Reinforcements were cut in 100 millimeters squares. To prepare samples of quite the same thickness, cut squares, of each reinforcement, had to be 2 millimeters thick, when squeezed with a caliper.

A thin, regular layer of the liquid divider was laid, using brush with hard bristle. The first layer of

reinforcement was put onto first layer of matrix. Reinforcement was spread and pressed against the

plate, to ensure that material was not rolled and there were no folds.

Table 1 Identities for samples manufactured for research.

		MATRIXES			
		MODOFEN TP	MODOFEN L	EPOLAM 2025	MODOFEN TP + MODEFEN L
REINFORCEMENTS	Ceramic paper	TP.C	L.PC	E.PC	TP+L.PC
	Glass fiber	TP.S	L.S	E.S	----
	Basalt fiber	TP.B	L.B	E.B	TP+L.B
	Wrapping paper	TP.PZ	----	E.PZ	TP+L.PZ

Table 2 Reinforcements physical properties

Property/material	Basalt fiber [14]	Glass fiber [15]	Wrapping paper [16]	Ceramic paper [16]		
Color	Light brown	White	Light brown	White		
Thickness [mm]	0,1	0,2	0,05	1		
Density [g/cm ³]	2,66	2,60	0,50	0,21		
Paper Substance [g/m ²]	-	-	50	-		
Tensile strength [MPa]	2700	1350	-	0,75		
Flexural Modulus [GPa]	85	75	-	-		
Hardness [Mohs scale]	8,5	-	-	-		
Elongation at break [%]	3,1	4,7	-			
Work temperature [°C]	-260÷750	-60÷380	-	÷1260		
Short-time work temperature [°C]	850	550	-	-		
Melting point [°C]	1460	1000	-	1760		
Thermal conductivity coefficient [W/(m·K)]	-	-	40°C	0,065	200°C	0,058
					300°C	0,074
					400°C	0,090
					500°C	0,110
					600°C	0,130
					800°C	0,195

This procedure accelerates a process of reinforcement infiltration. Because it was done with fingers, students had to wear latex gloves to avoid getting any dirt into samples. It was also very important to check if the weave of reinforcement such as glass fiber and basalt fiber was not damage, what could cause unevenness of the samples surface. After the first layer of reinforcement was fully infiltrated with resin, next layer of matrix was

applied, then next layer of reinforcement was laid and the whole, described operation was repeated till the last layer of prepared reinforcement was applied. Not hardened samples were covered with the duralumin plate of the same size as one from the bottom. Samples were squeezed, using bolts, between plates to ensure that their surface would be plain and there would be no air bubbles inside them.

Table 3 Matrixes physical properties

Property /material	EPOLAM 2025 Resin [17]		EEPOLAM 2025 Hardener [17]		EPOLAM 2025 Resin with EPOLAM 2025 Hardener – Cured Properties at 23°C [17]	MODOFEN L [18]		MODOFEN TP [19]	
Composition	Epoxy		Amine		-	-		-	
Mix ratio, by weight	100		28		-	-		-	
By volume	100		36		-	-		-	
Appearance	Liquid		Liquid		Solid	Liquid		Liquid	
Color	Off-white		Blue		Light blue	Orange-brown		Dark yellow to brown	
Viscosity	25°C [mPa·s] (Brookfield LVT)	6000	25°C [mPa·s] (Brookfield LVT)	18	-	23°C [mm ² /s]	620	20°C [mPa·s]	400÷600
Density [g/cm ³]	25°C (ISO 1675:1985)	1,19	25°C (ISO 1675:1985)	0,92	-	20°C	1,00÷1,10	20°C	1,15÷1,25
Boiling point [°C]	-		-		-	87		100	
Ignition point [°C]	-		-		-	-		62	
Self-ignition temperature at 992hPa [°C]	-		-		-	-		580	
Glass Transition Temperature (Tg) [°C]	-		-		135	-		-	
Hardness [Shore D]	-		-		87	-		-	
Tensile Strength [MPa]	-		-		56	-		-	
Elongation at break [%]	-		-		7	-		-	
Flexural Modulus [MPa]	-		-		3200	-		-	

Plates and bolts together made a mould. Inside this mould samples were hardening and put into furnace. Duralumin plates were big enough to hold three to four samples. Shorter plates had dimensions, which enabled to put them, with samples containing heat-hardening resin, into furnace. Usage of longer plates rather than separated plate for each sample had important advantage. Such plates are easier to bend. They are bending significantly in contrary to hardened samples, which are not elastic. This difference simplify the process of dividing samples from plates. Hardened samples were also not strongly connected to the surface of plates, because it was smooth and covered with the liquid divider.

All types of matrixes, that were used, had to be thermally processed. MODOFEN TP, MODOFEN L and MODOFEN TP mixed with MODOFEN L - phenol-formaldehyde resins are heat-hardening and samples containing them were hardened in the furnace in a temperature of about 170°C for about 30 minutes.

Samples containing epoxy resin EPOLAM 2025 harden within 24 hour in room temperature. After hardening, alumina plates were taken off and samples needed high-temperature postcure. It was done according to producers schedule with a recommended temperature ramp between each stage of 30°C/hour: 2 hours at 40°C, 2 hours at 60°C, 2 hours at 80°C, 2 hours at 100°C, 2 hours at 120°C. After that samples were cooled at maximum rate of 30°C/hour.

After hardening and taking of moulds samples had very irregular edges. To obtain uniform surface and thickness, samples were trimmed with precision grinder to 85 millimeters squares. 10 millimeters square samples were prepared to measure materials thermal diffusivity.

5. Laser flash thermal diffusivity measurement method

Laser Flash Analysis Method (LFA) was proposed by Parker (et al.) [7] in 1961 and until now it became very popular as effective and simple method to measure thermal diffusivity and thermal conductivity. Idea is straightforward; specimen is heated on one of its side with very short in time, high power density light impulse generated by laser or flash lamp. On the second side of the specimen, infrared detector measures time response of temperature signal. After that using theoretical methods and numerical tools diffusivity is obtained. Many improvements of the method were proposed

during methods' development. One of the most significant are time, ambient temperature and heat losses corrections by Cape and Lehmann [9] introduced in 1963. In the same year Cowan introduced corrections for heat losses and for high temperatures [10]. Further significant improvements for pulse-length in the Cape Lehmann model were introduced by Blumm and Opfermann in 2002 [11]. There is common approach to find thermal diffusivity corresponding to temperature on back surface when it equals half of maximum temperature: $T(L, t_{\frac{1}{2}}) = 0.5T_0$. In such case thermal diffusivity is given by formula [1], [6]:

$$\alpha = \frac{0.138785L^2}{\pi^2 t_{1/2}} \quad (8)$$

Thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity can be alternatively obtained using Eq. (1). Further improvements are necessary in modern approach to LFA. Effects of graphite coatings, radiation heat loses and others are included but the basic idea is straightforward [8-12].

6. Measurements results

Whole research was carried out using very precise devices. Thermal diffusivity was measured with the NETZSCH LFA 457 MicroFlash laser flash analysis equipment [13]. Measurements were conducted in temperature range from 50°C to 200°C. Figures 1-4 and Table 4 present the measurements results.

Figure 1 presents the measurements results for MODOFEN TP resin composites (TP composites). Thermal diffusivity (TD) of TP composites containing wrapping paper, basalt fiber and ceramic paper is very regular and does not change significantly with increasing temperature. The rise of the TD for samples containing ceramic paper, between 50°C and 200°C, reaches only 0,002mm²/s. This is the smallest change of TD of all examined materials. Also TP composites containing wrapping paper and basalt fiber have the smallest slop of TD with increasing temperature.

The change, between 50°C and 200°C, for both materials reaches 0,010mm²/s. Only samples containing glass fiber reaches TD slope of 0,023mm²/s, between 50°C and 200°C, which is comparable to materials containing different resins. For each TP composite the biggest change of TD appears between 50°C and 100°C. This relation is

Figure 1 Thermal diffusivity measurements for MODOFEN TP resin composites.

Figure 2 Thermal diffusivity measurements for MODOFEN L resin composites.

Figure 3 Thermal diffusivity measurements for EPOLAM 2025 resin composites.

Figure 4 Thermal diffusivity measurements for MODOFEN TP and MODOFEN L mixed resin composites.

also true for all other samples, regardless of matrix and reinforcement kind.

Figure 2 presents the measurements results for MODOFEN L resin composites (L composites). These materials containing ceramic paper, basalt fiber and glass fiber demonstrate the same relation with increasing temperature. Between 50°C and 150°C TD drops, reaching lowest value at 150°C and then it raises with temperature. The biggest observed change of TD for L composites has sample containing ceramic paper. Between 50°C and 150°C its TD value drops by 0,045mm²/s and then, between 150°C and 200°C, it raises by 0,017mm²/s. L composites have the highest value of TD from all samples, what means that they have the worst insulating properties.

Figure 3 presents the measurements results for EPOLAM 2025 resin composites (E composites). EPOLAM 2025 is the only epoxy resin in this research. E composites have the highest TD slope with temperature. It reaches 0,067mm²/s for samples containing glass fiber between 50°C and 200°C. TD raises only for samples containing ceramic paper between 150°C and 200°C. Although TD of E composites is quite high for 50°C, between 150°C and 200°C reaches the lowest values from all examined samples. E composites have the best insulating properties in high temperatures, especially this containing ceramic paper. Its TD reaches only 0,074mm²/s for 200°C.

Figure 4 presents the measurements results for MODOFEN L and MODOFEN TP mixed resin composites (TP+L composites). TDs of these materials have quite similar values. TD slope with increasing temperature can be observed for TP+L composites containing ceramic and wrapping paper. For sample containing basalt fiber TD raises slightly

by 0,001mm²/s between 150°C and 200°C. TP+L composite containing basalt fiber has lower TD, in the whole temperature range, than L and TP composites with same reinforcement. Also sample containing ceramic paper has the same feature for 100°C and 200°C. However samples containing wrapping paper have much higher TD than TP composites with same reinforcement. Mixing two phenol-formaldehyde resins can improve thermal insulating properties, when basalt fiber or ceramic paper are used as a reinforcement.

7. Conclusions

In combustion chamber of solid fuel rocket, during its operation temperature reaches very high values for quite short time. In such conditions thermal insulation should have as low as possible thermal diffusivity. According to research results, lowest thermal diffusivity, what means best thermal insulating properties, in temperature range from 100°C to 200°C, has EPOLAM 2025 resin reinforced with ceramic paper. It is recommended to use this material as a new thermal insulation for RS-SSA's, future rockets propelled with HP fuels. Worth mentioning are also results of MODOFEN TP and EPOLAM 2025 resins, both reinforced with wrapping paper. They have slightly worse thermal diffusivity results than EPOLAM 2025 resin reinforced with ceramic paper, but due to low wrapping paper price, can become cheaper alternative for ceramic paper reinforcement.

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